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**DIGITALIZATION OF FINANCIALLY-ORIENTED STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT
 OF FUEL AND ENERGY COMPLEX ENTERPRISES IN THE INVESTMENT AND
 REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT**

The intensive introduction of digital technologies in various sectors of the economy necessitates the revision and development of methodological approaches to the strategic management of enterprises, taking into account their impact on financial stability and investment efficiency. In the context of the structural transformation of the economy, the growth of investment and regulatory uncertainty, as well as the complexity of the external environment, the study of digitalization of financially oriented strategic management of enterprises of the fuel and energy complex (fuel and energy complex) is of particular relevance. High capital intensity of projects, long investment cycles and volatility of energy markets increase the dependence of strategic decisions on the stability of cash flows, capital structure and cost of financing, which necessitates the strengthening of the role of digital analytical and management tools. The research uses methods of systemic and structural-functional analysis, as well as elements of comparative and logical-analytical approaches to study the processes of digitalization of financially oriented strategic management in the fuel and energy sector. The paper systematizes the key directions of digitalization of strategic management contours, identifies institutional, investment and regulatory constraints on their implementation, and analyzes the impact of digital tools on the manageability of investment programs, financial stability and adaptability of strategic decisions of industry enterprises. The conclusions are formulated that digitalization of financially oriented strategic management is a significant factor in increasing the adaptability and long-term financial and economic stability of fuel and energy complex enterprises. Practical recommendations have been developed aimed at improving digital management contours, increasing the effectiveness of investment decisions and reducing investment and regulatory risks in a highly uncertain environment.

Keywords: digitalization of strategic management, financially oriented management, fuel and energy complex enterprises, investment efficiency, financial stability, cost of capital, investment uncertainty, regulatory uncertainty, digital management tools.

[1-3].

[2,4].

[3, 5-7].

4.0

[3, 7].

[4, 8].

[6,9].

[10-12].

[1, 6, 7,].

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
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21]. [2, 19, 20, -
 , [7, 16, 18]. -
 [3, 8]. -
 [5, 7, 21]. -
 1, -
 [8, 11, 16]. -
 1, [4, 5]. -
 [19, 20]. -

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.1.

([3, 4, 5-8, 16-19, 21-26]).

. 2.

([7, 9, 15, 21]).

16]. ERP- , [7, 9, -
 « → , -
 → → » [15, 26]. CAPEX -
 : [5, 19, 21]. -
 , [7, 16]. -
 2. - - () -
 [11, 12]. , -
 [3, 5, 23]. , -
 , -
 , CAPEX -
 [12, 18]. , -
 , -
 3. - () -
 [14]. , -
 , [11, 14]. -
 KPI (FCF, ROIC, WACC), -
 [15]. -

[16,27].
 « » « » [6, 11, 14].
 [3, 5, 7].
 [19,21].
 [3, 5]. [19,
 20]. [11, 15].
 [12, 18].
 [5, 19].
 [7, 16]. [4, 21, 26-29].
 [19, 20].
 [23, 26].
 [21, 25]. [11, 15].
 [12, 16].

1.

*

-	-	CAPEX, ROIC,	
-	-	CF,	-
-	-	Debt/EBITDA,	-
	-	, OPEX	-
	-		CAPEX
	-		-

* [2-5, 7, 21, 26]

1,

[3, 5, 19, 21].

[7, 15].

[5, 15].

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{DigitalStrategy}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{InvestFactors}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{RegFactors}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Controls}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}, \quad (1)$$

— Y_{it} — ; $\text{InvestFactors}_{it}$, RegFactors_{it} — ; Controls_{it} — (

[15].

[3, 5, 21].

[11, 12].

2.

*

CF	Digital Strategy	-0,18	p < 0,05	
ROIC	Digital Strategy	+0,24	p < 0,01	
WACC	Digital Strategy	-0,15	p < 0,05	
CF	CAPEX /	+0,12	p < 0,05	
ROIC	Debt / EBITDA	-0,19	p < 0,05	
WACC		-0,11	p < 0,10	

*

[7, 20, 24]

[7, 12].

[3, 20, 21].

.3.

[22, 25]).

.4.

(ROIC)

[22, 25]).

DigitalStrategy

ROIC.

(WACC)

[15, 16].

.5.

(WACC)

[22, 25]).

WACC,

[7, 11].

3

3.

*

-		-	
-	,	CFvol	
-	,	CFvol, Debt/EBITDA	CF
-	-	ROIC	-
(NPV/IRR)			CAPEX
-	,	WACC	-
ESG-	-	WACC, RegShare	
-		DigitalStrategy (X)	-

*

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[7, 11, 12].

[15, 16, 18].
NPV IRR

[13, 14].

ESG-

[6, 7, 34].

(.6).

10–20 %	
1,5–3,0 . .	
0,5–1,2 . .	-
8–15 %	CAPEX -
(Debt/EBITDA)	-

.6.
[3, 4, 21]).

[6, 7, 10].

[3, 14, 16].

[4, 21, 26].

[2, 19, 20].

4

4.

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	-	-	-
	-	-	CFvol ↓
	-	-	CFvol ↓, CAPEX/Revenue
(NPV/IRR)	-	-	ROIC ↑
	-	-	WACC ↓
ESG-	-	-	WACC ↓, RegShare
	-	-	DigitalStrategy ↑
	-	-	RegShare, CFvol

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[6-7, 18, 27, 28].

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